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CURRENT STATUS OF POPULATION INCOME FORMATION IN AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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Summary: *One of the main indicators characterizing the level of economic development of the country and the quality of life of citizens is the formation of population income. The article examines the main sources of income of the population in urban and rural areas, the direction in which their expenses are spent most, which part is allocated for savings, the share of population income in urban and rural areas, etc. The main indicator that has a positive impact on the increase in population income in our country in recent years is the expansion of employment and the increase in wages. However, along with this, inflation, price increases and economic differences across regions remain the main factors affecting the real purchasing power of income. Social protection measures implemented by the state, increasing the minimum wage and pensions are aimed at improving the well-being of the population.*

Keywords: *population income, sources of income, population groups, consumption expenditures, economic problems*

In modern conditions, income differences between population groups are considered to be one of the world's economic problems. Thus, the intensification of the growing stratification situation causes sharp protests from different class groups in different countries. For this purpose, various regulatory policies are being developed to reduce the speed of the stratification or completely eliminate this situation. There are different economic opinions on this. First of all, it would be useful to identify the main reasons for the growing inequality. According to some economists, the main reason for these growing differences is the difference in the level of wages paid to people working in different fields. According to the American economist, Nobel laureate (in 2001) G. Akerlof (1940), the level of effective wages is such a limit that the wages paid here coincide with the growth of national income. Otherwise, deviations can cause unreasonable changes in the commodity or money market. According to the scientist, although wage differentiation acts as a factor that serves to increase the labor productivity of employees, in some cases it accelerates an unhealthy struggle among employees for the achievement of high wages [4, s. 54-55].

However, after studying the topic for a while, it becomes clear that the main reason for the differences that arise is not due to the level of wages paid to people, but to the fact that each of them has their income formed from different sources. That is, each individual is not satisfied with just receiving a salary, but continues their lives by establishing activities in other areas. This ultimately leads to fundamental changes and differences in the amount of funds they receive in the future. Taking this into account, let's pay attention to the sources from which individuals' budget incomes are formed by legislation in our country. Of course, if we pay attention, although the sources of income of urban and rural residents are the same, there will be differences in the amounts of the sources they receive [5, s. 227]. That is, the income sources of people working in cities and people working in rural areas

will form their income in different proportions from the sources indicated. When paying attention to Table 1, it becomes clear that there is a fundamental difference here, both in the level of wages and in the distribution of funds received from other sources. When paying attention to the main sources of income of the population, it becomes clear that the source of income of 32.5% of the urban population is the funds received from hired work. When paying attention to the level of income of the rural population in the same area, it becomes clear that the share here is lower and is 23.0 percent. While the funds received from self-employment accounted for 18.4 percent of the total income of the urban population, the relative amount of funds received from self-employment activities of the population living in rural areas was 32.8 percent [10].

Table 1
Main sources of income of the population in urban and rural areas in 2024, in percentage

	Total by country	By urban areas	By rural areas
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0
wage employment	27.9	32.5	23.0
self-employment	25.3	18.4	32.8
production of goods for personal consumption	2.7	1.3	4.1
property and other capital investments	0.2	0.2	0.1
old-age labor pension	13.6	14.5	12.6
labor pension for the loss of the breadwinner	0.2	0.2	0.2
labor pension for disability	3.0	2.6	3.5
benefit for disability and for a child under 18 years of age with a disability	0.7	0.8	0.6
other benefits	0.9	0.8	1.0
educational pension	0.5	0.6	0.4
other pensions	0.2	0.2	0.2
unemployment insurance payment	0.1	0.1	0.1
targeted state social assistance	0.1	0.1	0.2
funds received from abroad	0.4	0.5	0.2
support of another person or persons	24.1	27.1	20.8
other	0.1	0.1	0.2

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Committee

In 2024, the population living in rural areas is in the forefront in terms of the level of income received from the production of products for personal consumption. Thus, in the current year, the population living in rural areas saved 4.1 percent of their expenses by consuming the products they produced themselves, which can also be characterized as their income. In the reporting year, income from the provision of old-age pensions, which is distinguished as an important direction of the income of family households, amounted to an average of 13.6 percent of the total income of families. Separately, this indicator amounted to 14.5 percent of the total income of families in urban areas, and 12.6 percent in rural areas. A striking point in Table 1 is the sharp decrease in the amount of funds provided for unemployment insurance in our country. At the same time, we can note the amount of targeted social assistance, which amounted to 0.1 percent of the total average income in the country from both sources. This shows us that a small part of family income is formed at the expense of transfer (socially targeted) payments [8].

Paying attention to the sources of income of the population, it is possible to see that despite the fact that the sources of income of the urban and rural population are the same, there are differences in the level of incomes. Especially among these sources of income, the low level of social payments, the high level of payments for the protection of individuals by other people and individuals, is not considered as a good thing. The high income generated from this type of source, from the free

payments as a result of the activities of third parties, allows the passivity of individuals, and this situation brings to the fore the importance of carrying out important work in the field of employment in the national economy of the country. In order to observe the situation more clearly, it is better to pay attention to the level of incomes and expenses of the country's population at current prices. With this, it is possible to clearly see what part of the total average income of different sections of the population in the country is spent and what part is collected. For this purpose, graph 1 shows the direction of the income and expenses of the country's population in the period of 2005-2024, and what part of them is directed to savings. First of all, if we pay attention to the base year, then we can see that the amount of income of the population in the country as a whole is slightly more than 8 billion manats. In that year, approximately 6.5 billion manats of the total revenues were spent and the remaining 1.5 billion manats were collected. In the next five years, the level of the population's income increased by 3.2 times, the level of consumer spending by 2.9 times, and savings by more than 4 times. The factor affecting the significant change of indicators in this way can be explained by the adoption of legislative acts in that period. In addition, the achievement of financial stability, bringing the employment of the population to a high level, led to a fundamental positive change of the indicator in this area. In 2022, the total income of the population was 55.7 billion manats, expenses were 49.8 billion manats, and collection was 5.9 billion manats. [7].

Chart 1

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Committee

The statistical flow of figures gives us reason to say that in fact, in response to the increased income level, the level of consumption expenditures has also increased. This, in turn, has led to a decrease, not an increase, in the amount of savings compared to the previous period. When looking at the reporting year, it is possible to see that a similar situation occurred during that period. Thus, in that year, the volume of total income was 68.9 billion manat, the amount of expenses was 65.7 billion manat, and savings were 3.15 billion manat. This fact indicates that substantial production is ensured in the national economy and that consumption expenditures have increased proportionally. The increase in consumption expenditures can be explained by the increase in the prices of products produced here and the increase in living standards. When considering the current state of the population's income, in order to ensure the relevance of the study, we think that it would be useful to address the issue of the income level of individual families, not the level of the state's total income. Therefore, let us pay attention to graph 2.1.1, which reflects the level of income per capita of the population living in the country over the past twenty-two years. When analyzing the numerical data

given in the graph, it becomes clear that in the base year, that is, in 2001, the amount of monthly income per capita in our country was 29.1 manat. It is an objective reality that the indicated figure is quite small. The explanation for such a low amount in a country that has just gained independence can be explained by the low level of wages against the background of the high level of unemployment in the country. In particular, the low rate of economic growth during that period, the realization of high inflation and the imperfect coordination of foreign economic relations were important factors affecting the increase in unemployment and the decrease in income. As a result of the favorable economic reforms carried out in our country over the next ten years, the amount of monthly wages per capita increased by approximately 5 (4.96) times. In the next decade, this indicator changed to positive by another 2.08 times. In the reporting year, that is, in 2022, the amount of monthly per capita income in households increased and reached 327.63 manat. Thus, it is clear that compared to 2001, the amount of per capita income in 2022 increased by approximately 11.3 times [8]. However, at the same time, it is clear from the previous graph that the increase in income did not increase the savings of individuals, but rather reduced them towards the future. Currently, research conducted in this field explains the reason for the decrease in the amount by the fact that the population makes savings towards the future not in money, but in the form of gold and property. On the other hand, the creation of new types of insurance organizations to insure against risks for various events has significantly reduced the amount of savings directed towards the future. This, in turn, indicates that the population is spending a significant portion of its income either on consumption or on long-term property purchases. It is clear from the data in Chart 2 that the factors influencing this increase in the monthly income level of households were both increases in the general level of prices and the solution to the employment problem of the population.

Chart 2

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Committee

Currently, the level of monthly income per capita in our country is increasing year by year. This can be explained by the significant increase in production of industrial and agricultural products in our country. After paying attention to the annual change in the level of income per capita, let us now pay attention to the level of expenditure per capita. When paying attention to the level of consumption expenditure per capita of the population in Chart 3 over the past twenty-two years, it becomes clear that in proportion to the change in the level of income, there have been various increases in the level of expenditure. In the base year, the amount of consumption expenditure per capita was 31.8 manat [1]. It can be seen that in that year, the amount of income per capita of households was 2.7 manat behind the expenditure incurred. From this, it can be asked that if the level of consumption income is

less than the expenditure, then how do households ensure this balance. If we pay attention, in the previous table (table 1) there are funds that are paid by another person or persons under their protection. With these funds, individuals can meet their needs at the necessary level. This actually eliminates the disagreement we have about how the resulting gap is eliminated. In the next five years, the level of monthly per capita household spending increased by 4.6 times. In the next ten years, that is, compared to 2010, the amount of per capita consumption spending in 2020 increased by about two times. Currently, in the current year, the total amount of this amount was at the level of 333.4 manats. The amount of the difference between per capita income and consumption spending in the current year is 5.77 manats, which is not considered a very high difference. The ratio of the resulting gap to income is about 1.7 percent, which is quite better than the rate accepted worldwide (10.5%).

Chart 3

Monthly per capita consumption expenditure in households for 2001-2024, manat

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Committee

In fact, there are numerous factors that have influenced the increase in the level of per capita consumption expenditure in recent years. Such factors can also be explained by the fact that the service sector has taken an important place in daily consumption due to the development of information technologies. Thus, the costs paid for services used in the daily service sector have a significant specific weight in consumption. This is explained by the fact that over time, the living conditions of the population have moved to the next stage due to international environmental factors [2, s. 73-74]. However, at the same time, the main factor influencing the sharp increase in the level of consumer spending is the increase in the prices of consumer goods in the world food market over time and the increase in the income level of the population. Today, in our country, in order to prevent the increase in consumer spending and to prevent this pace from becoming sharp over the years, state support is being provided in numerous ways aimed at reducing the cost of production of products. However, unfortunately, as in other regions of the world, it is not possible to prevent the increase in prices in our country [3, s. 256]. Therefore, meeting consumption expenses by increasing the income of the population in our country has been identified as an important direction.

Table 2

Population income by urban and rural areas in 2024

	total by country	including	
		places in the city	in rural areas

	2024/ 2023, %	2023	2024	2024/ 2023, %	2023	2024	2023/ 2024, %
Income – total	109.0	311.13	339.98	109.3	288.74	312.73	108.3
Income from wage employment	114.5	137.92	157.33	114.1	75.06	84.04	112.0
Income from self-employment	106.7	77.29	83.29	107.8	127.63	137.11	107.4
Income from agricultural production	102.7	6.47	6.74	104.2	65.29	69.15	105.9
Income from property – total	108.0	1.46	1.56	106.8	0.77	0.81	105.2
Income from rental of property	106.6	0.96	1.01	105.2	0.55	0.58	105.5
Current transfers received	103.5	63.46	65.09	102.6	57.95	60.49	104.4
Pensions	102.4	56.72	57.52	101.4	46.09	47.50	103.1
Benefits, scholarships and other social payments	108.1	6.44	7.20	111.8	11.54	12.42	107.6
Monetary value of in-kind receipts	151.6	0.30	0.37	123.3	0.32	0.57	178.1
Other income	108.0	31.00	32.71	105.5	27.33	30.28	110.8
Received funds from other households within the country	107.8	26.44	27.73	104.9	21.49	23.92	111.3
Received funds from abroad	108.7	4.56	4.98	109.2	5.84	6.36	108.9

Source: Compiled based on data from the State Statistics Committee

If we pay attention to the sources of income of the urban and rural population in our country, we will see that certain changes have occurred in this area in the last year. When we pay attention to the data in Table 2, it becomes clear that compared to 2023, there was a 9.0% increase in the amount of total income in the country. This figure was 8.3 percent in the income of people living in rural areas, and 9.3 percent in the income of people living in urban areas. Compared to the base year, the total amount of self-employment income increased by 6.7 percent in the country, 7.4 percent in rural areas separately, and 7.8 percent in the urban population. The level of income from sources related to the use of property increased by 8.0%, and the level of funds received from transfer payments increased by 3.5 percent. Here, the income of the population of retirement age increased by 2.4 percent. A similar situation was observed in the income of both the urban and rural population. The analysis of the data in Table 2 also showed us that there was a significant increase in the amount of benefits, pensions and other social payments. It showed that the amount of income from these sources has increased significantly. It provided the necessary information about the increase in the amount of funds received both from within the country and from abroad in the last year. Thus, it became clear from which sources the income of the population was actually formed. Awareness was provided about the direction in which incomes changed. The role of the state and personal initiative in this area was clarified.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. “2008–2015-ci illərdə Yoxsulluğun azaldılması və davamlı inkişaf üzrə Dövlət Proqramı”. 15 sentyabr 2008-ci il.
2. “Büdcə sistemi haqqında” Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. 2 iyul 2002-ci il.
3. “Dövlət büdcəsinin icrası haqqında” Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. 29 may 2015-ci il.
4. Кушлина В. Государственное регулирование рыночной экономики / Под ред. РАГС. – М., 2005. – 534 с.
5. Культурная политика в Азербайджанской Республике. – Баку: Министерство культуры Азербайджанской Республики, 2009. – 106 с.
6. Nəsimov X. Azərbaycan iqtisadiyyatı. – Bakı, 2005. – 327 s.
7. Рисина И. Государственное регулирование экономики: учебное пособие / под ред. – М.: КНОРУС, 2014. – 240 с.
8. Ровенского М. Кредит и банки: учебник. – М.: Проспект, 2016. – 315 с.
9. Şəkəraliyev A., Şəkəraliyev Q. Azərbaycan iqtisadiyyatı: reallıqlar və perspektivlər. – Bakı: Turxan NPB, 2016. – 536 s.
10. economy.gov.az
11. meclis.gov.az